
HERITAGE DATA PROCESSOR (HDP): A MODULAR ARCHITECTURE FOR PROCESSING AND PERSISTENTLY STORING MULTIMODAL CULTURAL HERITAGE DATA

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Abstract

The acceleration of data acquisition technologies within the Digital Humanities has precipitated a proliferation of heterogeneous research assets, creating significant challenges for long-term preservation and repository ingestion. Existing workflows, frequently dependent on ephemeral scripting and manual curation, fail to guarantee the reproducibility and structural integrity required by trusted digital repositories. This paper details the Heritage Data Processor (HDP), a modular architectural framework designed to automate the preservation of multimodal cultural heritage data to the Zenodo infrastructure. Distinguishing itself from monolithic legacy tools, the system implements a persistent project state through a SQLite-based container format, thereby decoupling local data management from immediate network dependencies. The architecture utilizes a component-based pipeline strategy to enforce strict dependency isolation, facilitating the integration of diverse processing tasks ranging from high-throughput 3D rendering to AI-driven metadata extraction. By formalizing the transition from raw operational storage to archival records, the HDP establishes a standardized protocol that enhances compliance with FAIR principles and ensures the functional longevity of digital heritage collections.

Keywords Software · Cultural Heritage · Data Processing · Persistence · Storage

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1 Introduction

The rapid digitization of cultural heritage has precipitated a fundamental shift in the scale and complexity of research data within the Digital Humanities (DH). As storage capacities expand and acquisition technologies become ubiquitous, spanning high-resolution photogrammetry, multispectral imaging, and spatialized multidimensional audio, researchers are confronted with an increasingly heterogeneous landscape of digital assets. While the production of such data has accelerated considerably, the workflows required to curate, standardize, and preserve it according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) [1] have often lagged behind. Current practices frequently rely on ad-hoc scripts and manual intervention, which compromise both efficiency and reproducibility.

This paper introduces the *Heritage Data Processor* (HDP), a modular, pipeline-driven architecture designed to bridge the operational gap between local data management and long-term preservation repositories.

1.1 The Challenge of Heterogeneous Heritage Data

Modern heritage datasets are characterized by substantial complexity and a lack of uniformity. They encompass a diverse array of modalities, spanning high-resolution photography, three-dimensional models, audio recordings, audiovisual documentation, and structured textual data. This heterogeneity creates significant impediments to the publication and archival process. For instance, a single three-dimensional digital artifact is rarely a solitary file; rather, it is a complex aggregate involving geometry data (such as Wavefront .obj), material libraries (.mtl), and texture maps. These components must be maintained as a coherent conceptual unit to ensure future computational reproducibility and visual fidelity.

A critical systemic challenge arises from the disconnect between the raw operational storage of these assets and the rigorous metadata schemata mandated by trusted digital repositories. Researchers frequently encounter difficulties in maintaining the semantic lineage between a digital object and its descriptive metadata, such as provenance and authorship, during the ingest phase. Furthermore, the absence of standardized configurations for validating specific data types frequently results in inconsistent data quality and ingestion errors. In the absence of automated validation and structural integrity checks, the long-term utility and reusability of archived heritage data remain compromised.

1.2 Evolution from Scripts to Systems: Zenodo Toolbox

The architectural design of the HDP represents an evolutionary successor to the Zenodo Toolbox [2]. Originally implemented as a Python module, this toolbox was engineered to facilitate large-scale batch processing and bulk ingestion into the Zenodo repository [3]. Although effective for targeted automation tasks, the utility displayed critical architectural constraints inherent to its script-based origins.

Primarily, the initial iteration lacked a mechanism for persistent project state management, relying solely on a monolithic SQLite database for record-keeping. In the absence of a dedicated serialization format for projects, metadata and processing configurations remained ephemeral. These configurations persisted only as logs of upload operations, lacking the contextual continuity required for iterative research workflows. Furthermore, the unified software design precipitated significant challenges regarding maintainability. As the toolkit expanded to encompass diverse data processing tasks, the accumulation of conflicting libraries within a singular Python environment resulted in unresolvable dependency conflicts. In this scenario, updates required for specific functionalities frequently compromised the stability of adjacent components.

An intermediate, unpublished iteration of the Zenodo Toolbox introduced an interactive Command-Line Interface (CLI) and implemented persistent project files to address state management. However, the fundamental issue of monolithic dependency management remained unresolved. Additionally, a critical usability barrier persisted: despite the provision of multiple Jupyter Notebooks containing simplified examples and workflow templates, the script-based and command-line interfaces remained inaccessible to researchers without programming expertise. This accessibility gap represented a significant impediment to broader

adoption within the Digital Humanities community, where domain specialists often lack formal training in computational methods.

1.3 The Heritage Data Processor (HDP) Solution

The Heritage Data Processor (HDP) addresses legacy limitations through a comprehensive architectural philosophy centered on persistent state management, strict component isolation, and versatile deployment capabilities. The system offers a unified operational framework accessible via a Graphical User Interface (GUI), a CLI, and an Application Programming Interface (API), ensuring functional congruence across all interaction modalities.

1. **Persistent Project Management:** Central to the HDP workflow is the `.hdpc` (Heritage Data Processor Container) project file. Unlike its predecessors, HDP utilizes this SQLite-based structure to store not only file inventories and metadata mappings but also the complete processing history and configuration state of a dataset. This persistent architecture facilitates asynchronous workflows, allowing data preparation, validation, and publication to span extended periods without loss of contextual integrity.
2. **Encapsulated Modular Architecture:** To eliminate dependency conflicts, HDP adopts a rigorously modular design. Processing logic is encapsulated within independent units designated as **HDP Components**. Each component is defined by a YAML [4] interface specification and executed within isolated environments, utilizing either ‘uv’-managed virtual environments [5] or Docker containers [6]. This isolation allows disparate components to operate with conflicting dependencies or distinct Python versions while remaining orchestratable by a central pipeline manager.
3. **Scalable Deployment and Integration:** The HDP architecture is agnostic to its hosting environment, capable of operating as a standalone desktop application, a server-side backend for web services, or within High-Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructures. Furthermore, it provides a robust bridge to Zenodo, supporting both Sandbox and Production environments. The system automates the complex lifecycle of repository records, from initial draft creation to versioned publication, ensuring precise DOI assignment and continuous metadata synchronization.

By formalizing these processes into a versatile environment that supports both interactive and script-based operation, HDP standardizes the preservation of complex heritage data, ensuring it remains accessible and interoperable for future research applications.

2 System Architecture and Implementation

The HDP is engineered based on core principles of modularity, portability, and robust state management. It is implemented as a hybrid desktop application that decouples the user interface from the core processing logic, a significant departure from the transient, script-based nature of its predecessors. This architecture is designed to satisfy the dual requirements of a responsive, cross-platform user interface and high-performance data processing.

2.1 Technology Stack and Hybrid Application Structure

To achieve a strict separation of concerns, the HDP employs a bifurcated structure, separating a frontend built on web-standard technologies from a dedicated Python backend for system-level computation [7].

The frontend is developed using the Electron framework [8], which facilitates cross-platform deployment by combining a Chromium rendering engine [9] with a Node.js runtime [10]. To ensure lightweight performance and maintainability, the interface avoids complex single-page application frameworks, instead relying on

standard ECMAScript (ES6+) with ES Modules (ESM) for its logical structure [11]. The visual design is implemented with Tailwind CSS [12], a utility-first styling framework.

This frontend communicates with the Python backend via a local RESTful API [13]. The backend, built upon the Flask web framework [14], is responsible for the computational workload, including file system scanning, metadata extraction, and pipeline execution. To enhance user interface responsiveness, the frontend directly integrates `sql.js`, a WebAssembly-based [15] implementation of SQLite [16]. This allows the application to perform direct, low-latency read operations on the local `.hdpc` project database, minimizing inter-process communication for data-querying tasks and offloading read operations from the Python backend.

HDP Technology Stack & Architecture

Figure 1: **Architectural overview of the Heritage Data Processor (HDP).** The diagram illustrates the hybrid application structure, decoupling the Electron-based frontend (handling UI and direct data reads via `sql.js`) from the Python backend (responsible for processing logic and database write operations). Inter-process communication is mediated by a local RESTful API, with the `.hdpc` SQLite database serving as the shared persistent storage layer.

2.1.1 Dependency Management

Given the complexity of heritage data workflows, rigorous dependency management is essential to prevent environment conflicts and ensure reproducibility. The HDP employs distinct strategies for frontend and backend dependencies. Frontend libraries are managed via `npm` [17], following standard Node.js conventions. For backend environment management, the system adopts `uv`, a high-performance Python package installer and environment manager.

The use of `uv` facilitates the rapid creation of isolated virtual environments (`.venv`) [18] based on the `pyproject.toml` specification [19], ensuring that the HDP’s dependencies remain isolated from system-level Python installations. This isolation is particularly critical for the modular HDP Components, which may require conflicting library versions. For instance, different processing components might depend on incompatible versions of widely used libraries such as `pandas` [20] or `numpy` [21], conflicts that are resolved through encapsulated environments.

2.1.2 System Dependencies

Beyond language-specific package management, the HDP integrates system-level tools to ensure robust and platform-agnostic data handling. A critical dependency is `libmagic` [22], the C library underlying the `file` command on Unix-like systems. This library provides definitive file type identification based on file signatures (byte-level patterns within the file header), rather than relying on potentially misleading file extensions. The HDP accesses this functionality via `python-magic` [23], a Python wrapper for the underlying system library. This capability is essential for digital preservation workflows, as it ensures that MIME types recorded in metadata accurately reflect the true format of digital objects across different operating systems, including macOS, Linux, and Windows.

2.2 Data Persistence: The `.hdpc` Database

State management within the HDP represents a fundamental departure from the ephemeral, file-based approaches of its predecessors. The system introduces the `.hdpc` file format, which functions as a portable, self-contained project database.

Technically, an `.hdpc` file is implemented as a SQLite relational database. This design choice provides transactional integrity and supports complex relational queries that flat file formats such as JSON or YAML cannot accommodate. The database schema organizes project data into several core relational tables:

- `project_info`: Stores high-level project metadata, including the project name, short code, and schema version.
- `source_files`: Maintains a comprehensive inventory of all local assets, tracking absolute file paths, computed SHA-256 cryptographic hashes [24], MIME types [25], and processing statuses (e.g., pending, valid, processed).
- `zenodo_records`: Manages the publication lifecycle, linking local file sets to Zenodo draft identifiers, Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) [26], and metadata snapshots.
- `record_files_map`: A relational join table that handles the many-to-one association between source files and Zenodo records, tracking the upload status of individual assets within a deposit.

Beyond portability, the SQLite architecture enables advanced project consolidation capabilities. In mass-digitization workflows, operators frequently create distinct projects for individual physical objects to ensure logical isolation during data acquisition. The HDP supports the merging of these disparate `.hdpc` files into a unified master database. This functionality permits a decentralized creation workflow, where individual datasets can be combined subsequently for bulk processing and unified publication. Critically, this consolidation preserves relational integrity and avoids data duplication, ensuring that provenance chains and processing histories remain intact across merged projects.

2.2.1 Schema Versioning and Migration

To ensure longitudinal software compatibility and the preservation of project data integrity, the HDP incorporates a rigorous database migration strategy utilizing **Alembic** [27]. As the software evolves, for instance by introducing new columns to the `zenodo_records` table to support additional metadata standards or repository features, the internal structure of the `.hdpc` container must be updated without compromising existing user data.

Upon initializing a project file, the application compares the revision identifier stored within the database against the schema definition of the current software version. If a version discrepancy is detected, the system automatically initiates an idempotent migration routine. Alembic executes the necessary upgrade scripts to modify the table structure transactionally. This process ensures that a project created with an older version of the HDP remains fully operational in the latest release. This approach effectively prevents the "format

obsolescence” frequently encountered in ad-hoc scripting tools, guaranteeing that the persistent project state remains accessible throughout the software’s lifecycle.

2.3 Configuration Management

The HDP implements a dynamic configuration system designed to balance operational usability with security best practices.

2.3.1 Dynamic Configuration and Runtime Reloading

Application-wide settings, such as server ports, default directory paths, and user interface preferences, are persisted in a `config.yaml` file. The system features a **Settings API** that supports dynamic runtime reloading, allowing users to modify configuration parameters without requiring a restart of the backend server. When a save request is issued to the `/config/save` endpoint, the system securely updates the configuration file, creates a backup of the previous state, and reinitializes the application context to apply changes immediately.

2.3.2 Security and Credential Isolation

To adhere to strict security standards regarding credential management, sensitive authentication tokens are explicitly segregated from the application’s source code and general configuration files. Specifically, Zenodo Personal Access Tokens must be defined in a separate environment file, `zenodo.env`, or within the user’s system environment variables.

The `zenodo.env` file is explicitly excluded from version control systems via configuration (e.g., `.gitignore`) [28]. The application loads these credentials into environment variables at runtime, ensuring that tokens for both the **Sandbox** (deposit:write scope) and **Production** environments are accessible to the API services while remaining protected from unintended disclosure or accidental public exposure.

2.4 Deployment and Lifecycle Automation

To guarantee the stability of the hybrid application architecture outlined in subsection 2.1, the HDP integrates a rigorous suite of lifecycle management utilities. These scripts abstract the inherent complexity of the dual-stack environment (Python and Node.js), mitigating the fragility of manual deployment by enforcing deterministic, automated processes.

2.4.1 Automated Provisioning and Validation

The installation procedure is governed by the `install_hdp.sh` script, which enforces a strict “pre-flight” validation protocol prior to any file modification. This routine verifies essential system prerequisites, including the presence of `git`, `uv`, and `npm`, while simultaneously validating available disk resources and network connectivity. To facilitate reproducibility, the script provides an interactive version selection interface that allows users to deploy specific tagged releases or the latest development branch. Additionally, a non-interactive mode is available to support seamless integration into CI/CD pipelines.

For development environments, the specialized `install_server.sh` script manages the installation of server components in “editable mode”. Unlike the standard production installer, this script leverages `pyproject.toml` for dependency resolution. It also supports a `--force` flag to regenerate virtual environments entirely, ensuring the development state remains consistent with the underlying codebase.

2.4.2 Runtime Integrity Enforcement

To prevent runtime failures resulting from environmental drift, application initialization is mediated by the `start_hdp.sh` wrapper. This script performs startup validation by verifying the integrity of the `.venv` virtual environment and confirming that all dependencies defined in `requirements.txt` correspond to the installed

versions. For enhanced production stability, the script implements a `--strict` mode. This mode elevates version mismatches from warnings to critical errors, thereby preventing the application from initializing in an unstable state.

2.4.3 Transactional Maintenance and Rollback

To address the challenges associated with maintaining long-running installations, the `update_hdp.sh` script utilizes a transactional update mechanism. It employs a "safety-first" strategy that automatically generates a backup of the local state via `git stash` before applying any modifications. The update logic supports configurable cleanup strategies, ranging from "clean-all" for pristine environments to "preserve-untracked" for retaining user configuration files, ensuring that local data is not inadvertently purged during updates. Crucially, the script includes an automatic rollback function; if an error occurs at any stage of the update process, the system reverts to the previous stable state using the cached stash, thus preserving operational continuity.

3 Data Organization Paradigms

The HDP establishes structured paradigms for conceptualizing and organizing digital heritage assets for preservation. Moving beyond simple file storage, the system enforces consistency across heterogeneous datasets while accommodating the complex, multi-file nature of digital artifacts.

3.1 Project Initialization and Modalities

The initialization of an HDP project is governed by the selection of *Modality Templates*. These templates function as preset configurations that define the primary characteristics of the dataset, ranging from *3D Model* and *Image / Photography* to *Text / Document* and *Multimodal Dataset*.

Rather than serving merely as descriptive metadata, these modalities actively configure the application's scanning heuristics and validation logic. For instance, selecting the *3D Model* modality pre-configures the system to recognize geometry file extensions (e.g., `.obj`, `.ply`, `.glb`). It also enables verification logic to confirm the presence of dependent assets, such as material libraries (`.mtl`) and texture maps. Crucially, these modalities are composable; a project may combine *Text* and *Image* templates, merging their respective validation rules to support complex research outputs such as digitized manuscripts with distinct transcription files.

To enforce rigorous data management standards, HDP mandates the definition of a *Project Short Code* during initialization. This concise, alphanumeric identifier (e.g., `scan05_2023`) serves as a unique namespace prefix for the project. The short code is utilized systematically throughout the application to prevent file-naming collisions in shared storage environments and to ensure a predictable directory layout for generated outputs.

3.2 Batch Entity Modes: Conceptualizing the Record

A critical challenge in digital preservation is defining the atomic unit of publication, the *Record*. HDP addresses this through configurable *Batch Entity Modes*, which determine how the physical file system structure maps to conceptual archival records.

3.2.1 Root Mode

In *Root Mode*, the system treats each individual file within the input directory as a distinct, standalone record. This paradigm is optimized for homogeneous datasets in which each asset is conceptually independent, such as a flat collection of archival photographs or scanned documents.

3.2.2 Subdirectory Mode

In *Subdirectory Mode*, the conceptual boundary shifts from the file to the folder. Each subdirectory within the input path is treated as a single record, aggregating all contained files into one preservation unit. This approach is essential for compound assets, such as photogrammetric 3D models, where the geometry, textures, and documentation must remain bundled to preserve the object’s integrity.

3.2.3 Hybrid Mode

In *Hybrid Mode*, the system combines both logics to accommodate heterogeneous datasets. It processes root-level files as individual records while simultaneously treating subdirectories as aggregated bundles. This flexibility enables researchers to manage mixed datasets, containing both standalone artifacts and complex multi-file entities, within a single project architecture.

3.3 Bundling Strategies

Within the defined entity modes, HDP implements advanced bundling algorithms to automatically associate related files, thereby reducing manual curation effort.

3.3.1 Stem Matching

The default strategy, *Stem Matching*, operates by linking files that share an identical base filename but differ in file extension. For example, in a typical 3D digitization workflow, the files `model_01.obj`, `model_01.mtl`, and `model_01.jpg` are automatically recognized as a coherent bundle. This behavior aligns with standard naming conventions generated by most digitization software and scanning equipment.

3.3.2 Pattern and Regex Matching

For datasets with complex or non-standard naming conventions, HDP supports regex-based bundling strategies that provide greater flexibility. The `prefix_suffix` strategy strips variable elements, such as version numbers (`v1_`) or resolution tags (`_highRes`), to identify the core identifier and group disparate file variants. For instance, files such as `v1_scan.obj` and `v2_scan.obj` can be aggregated into a single versioned record. Additionally, the `core_identifier` strategy enables the extraction of embedded identifiers (e.g., `site042`) to group all matching assets regardless of their descriptive suffixes or prefixes.

3.3.3 Primary Source Designation

To anchor multi-file bundles, HDP introduces the concept of the *Primary Source File*. Within any bundle containing multiple files, one specific file extension (e.g., `.obj` for 3D models, `.tiff` for high-resolution images) is designated as the primary entry point. This designation serves two critical functions. First, the primary source file acts as the reference key for metadata mapping, enabling the system to link the entire bundle to a corresponding row in an external metadata file (e.g., CSV). Second, it initiates a hierarchical dependency scan, allowing the system to verify that all referenced secondary assets, such as texture maps defined in an MTL file, are present and internally consistent.

4 Metadata Engineering and Automation

The rigorous curation of descriptive metadata is a prerequisite for FAIR data compliance. However, manual metadata entry is error-prone and inherently unscalable for large-scale heritage datasets. The HDP addresses this challenge by implementing a sophisticated abstraction layer that automates the translation of local, unstructured project data into the standardized schema required by the Zenodo repository. This approach

directly supports the requirement for communities to define machine-actionable templates that capture harmonized metadata [29].

4.1 The Metadata Mapping Wizard

The core component of this abstraction layer is the Metadata Mapping Wizard. Rather than requiring users to manually populate fields for individual records, the system enables the definition of a persistent *translation logic* stored within the `.hdpc` database. This architecture ensures that the metadata generation process remains transparent and reproducible, satisfying the FAIR requirement for rich metadata (F2) that facilitates precise findability [29]. The wizard abstracts the complexity of the JSON-based Zenodo schema through configurable *Mapping Primitives*:

- **Column-based Mapping:** This primitive links a specific column in the source spreadsheet (e.g., `Object_ID`) to a Zenodo metadata field. It supports concatenation operations, ensuring that the semantic richness of local data is preserved during the mapping to generic schemas.
- **Literal Values and Controlled Vocabularies:** To ensure interoperability (I2), the system enforces the use of controlled vocabularies for fields such as *Resource Type* or *License*. By validating these inputs against the repository API, HDP prevents the creation of "false agreements" or ambiguous labels that hinder machine readability [29].
- **Filename Derivation:** Recognizing that file naming conventions often encode semantic information, HDP allows metadata to be extracted directly from the filename stem.
- **Complex Hierarchical Mapping:** For nested entities (e.g., Contributors), HDP supports structured mapping. This capability is critical for FAIR Principle F3, ensuring that metadata clearly and explicitly includes the unique identifiers (e.g., ORCIDs) of the agents related to the data [29].

4.2 Automated Enrichment and LLM Integration

Beyond static mapping, the HDP architecture incorporates dynamic strategies for metadata enrichment, utilizing both algorithmic heuristics and integration with Large Language Models (LLMs).

4.2.1 Constructed Fields and Templates

To handle fields that require narrative structure, such as the *Description*, HDP implements a "Construct Later" logic based on dynamic templates. Users can define string templates containing variable placeholders (e.g., "Zenodo record for the data file: `${title}`"). These placeholders are resolved at the moment of metadata preparation, allowing the system to programmatically generate unique, context-aware descriptions for each record by retrieving values from other mapped fields or file attributes.

4.2.2 Automapping Algorithms

The `utils_api` module implements an automapping algorithm designed to minimize configuration overhead. Upon loading a metadata spreadsheet, the system analyzes the header row using a four-level matching strategy to automatically suggest mappings to Zenodo fields.

The algorithm proceeds through the following heuristic levels:

1. **Exact Match:** A direct string equality check.
2. **Normalized Match:** A comparison of lowercase, stripped strings (removing underscores and spaces).
3. **Pluralization Match:** Handling of simple plural forms (e.g., mapping "Keywords" to "Keyword").

4. **Fuzzy Similarity Match:** Utilizing the `difflib.SequenceMatcher` algorithm [30, 31] with a confidence threshold of 0.8 to identify semantically similar headers (e.g., mapping "Author Name" to an instance of "Creators").

4.2.3 Local LLM Integration

Recognizing the potential of LLMs in metadata curation, HDP integrates support for local or remote Large Language Models, currently via the **Ollama** framework [32], which is planned to be extended by **vLLM** [33, 34]. The system can interface with arbitrary models with small models running locally to perform semantic tasks. This architectural support enables advanced functionalities defined in the configuration, such as analyzing file content to suggest relevant keywords or generating abstractive descriptions. This augments standard metadata with AI-derived context while maintaining data privacy by keeping processing local. Crucially, these generative outputs are not accepted blindly; they are subjected to the strict schema validation protocols detailed in subsection 4.3.

4.3 Schema Validation and Integrity Enforcement

To ensure that metadata generated through both manual and automated processes conforms to repository requirements, HDP implements a multi-layered validation framework. This framework operates as a quality gate, preventing the submission of malformed or incomplete metadata to the Zenodo repository.

4.3.1 Structural Validation

The first validation layer performs structural checks against the Zenodo metadata schema. The system verifies that all required fields are present and that data types conform to expected formats (e.g., dates in ISO 8601 format, integers for numeric identifiers). This validation is enforced through JSON Schema definitions that mirror the official Zenodo API specification [35], ensuring compatibility with repository requirements.

4.3.2 Semantic Validation

Beyond structural correctness, the system performs semantic validation to verify that field values are meaningful and conform to controlled vocabularies. For instance, the validator confirms that license identifiers correspond to recognized SPDX 3.0 (Software Package Data Exchange) codes [36, see also 37] and that resource type designations match the repository's enumerated options. This prevents the submission of arbitrary strings that would reduce discoverability and interoperability.

4.3.3 Relational Integrity Checks

The validation framework also enforces relational consistency between metadata fields. For example, if a record declares a primary file with extension `.obj`, the system verifies that any referenced dependencies (e.g., material libraries or texture files) are present in the associated bundle and correctly specified in the metadata. This cross-validation ensures that compound digital objects remain internally coherent throughout the preservation workflow.

4.3.4 LLM Output Verification

For metadata generated or enriched through LLM integration, additional validation steps are applied. The system checks that AI-generated content adheres to length constraints, does not contain prohibited characters or formatting artifacts, and maintains semantic consistency with the source data. Generative outputs are flagged for manual review when confidence scores fall below configurable thresholds, ensuring that human oversight is preserved for critical descriptive fields.

The validation results are presented to users through an interactive review interface, which highlights errors

and warnings with actionable remediation suggestions. Records that fail validation are prevented from progressing to the publication stage, maintaining the integrity of the archival repository.

5 The Modular Pipeline Ecosystem

The HDP diverges from monolithic predecessors through a rigorously modular pipeline ecosystem. This architecture enables the encapsulation of discrete processing tasks, such as 3D format conversion, metadata extraction, or image validation, into interchangeable units that can be orchestrated into complex, automated workflows.

5.1 Component Architecture: The Triad Structure

At a granular level, the ecosystem is built upon standardized HDP Components. To ensure interoperability and maintainability, each component adheres to a strict three-tier architectural pattern that enforces a separation of concerns between specification, interface, and implementation.

Figure 2: **The HDP Component Architecture Triad.** This diagram illustrates the three-tiered modular structure designed to enforce a strict separation of concerns within the pipeline ecosystem. **Layer 1 (Specification)** establishes `component.yaml` as the single source of truth, defining input/output contracts and triggering the creation of isolated execution environments via `uv`. **Layer 2 (Interface)** functions as the translational bridge, where `main.py` utilizes `argparse` to enforce strict congruency between the abstract YAML definitions and concrete CLI arguments. **Layer 3 (Logic)** encapsulates the computational core within `processor.py`, maintaining a class-based structure that ensures the algorithmic logic remains decoupled, testable, and reusable in external Python contexts.

- **The Specification Layer (`component.yaml`):** This YAML file serves as the single source of truth for the component. It rigorously defines the component’s metadata (e.g., version, author), input requirements (e.g., file types, directory paths), output specifications (e.g., MIME types, naming patterns), and parameter groups (e.g., drop-downs, booleans). Crucially, it also declares system dependencies and Python packages, allowing the system to provision isolated execution environments.
- **The Interface Layer (`main.py`):** Functioning as the entry point, this script acts as a CLI wrapper. It utilizes `argparse` to translate the abstract definitions within the YAML specification into concrete

Figure 3: **Schematic representation of HDP Batch Entity Modes.** The diagram illustrates the three structural paradigms used to map local file systems to archival records. **Root Mode** maps individual files to distinct records (1:1). **Subdirectory Mode** aggregates entire folders into single compound records (n:1), ensuring that multi-file assets like 3D models remain semantically linked. **Hybrid Mode** enables the simultaneous processing of both structures to handle mixed datasets.

command-line arguments. This layer is responsible for input validation, argument parsing, and instantiating the core processor class. A strict congruency is enforced here: every parameter defined in `component.yaml` must have a corresponding handler in `main.py`.

- **The Logic Layer (`processor.py`):** This layer contains the computational logic, implemented as a class-based structure. By decoupling the algorithmic core from the CLI interface, the processor remains technology-agnostic and testable, facilitating its reuse in other Python contexts external to the HDP environment.

5.2 The Centralized Registry Middleware

To decouple local processing clients from the latency and strict rate-limiting constraints of the Zenodo API, the ecosystem relies on a centralized middleware service, the *HDP Component Registry*. This service is architected as a lightweight, containerized microservice utilizing the Flask framework.

5.2.1 Asynchronous Synchronization and Integrity Verification

Unlike a passive database, the Registry actively maintains synchronization with the *hdp-components* Zenodo Community¹ through an autonomous background scheduler. Implemented via the `APScheduler` library, the `SchedulerService` executes periodic update cycles (configurable via `UPDATE_INTERVAL_HOURS`, typically 24 hours).

Crucially, the synchronization process implements a strict **Supply Chain Security** protocol to mitigate the risk of arbitrary code execution. During the update cycle, the `ZenodoService` does not merely download assets; it enforces a cryptographic handshake. The system calculates the SHA-256 checksum of the downloaded `component_complete.zip` and validates it against a trusted, immutable ledger of signed releases maintained by the community moderator. This ensures that even if a community contributor's Zenodo account is compromised, malicious code cannot be injected into the ecosystem, as the modified archive would fail the signature verification step and be rejected by the Registry.

5.2.2 Unified Discovery Endpoint

The aggregated and validated metadata is served through a high-performance REST endpoint, `/hdp/v1/available-components`. This endpoint provides HDP clients with a unified, categorized manifest of all valid HDP Components, including their version history, direct download links, and calculated dependency trees. By consolidating discovery and security logic into this middleware, the system ensures that end-users interact with a cached, verified state of the ecosystem. This significantly improves the responsiveness of the pipeline construction interface while maintaining a secure chain of custody.

5.3 Component Implementation Case Study: The Fast Renderer

To illustrate the practical application of the three-tier architecture, we examine the *Fast Renderer* component [38]. This high-throughput 3D visualization tool was designed to evaluate the limits of the HDP's modular capabilities. The component encapsulates the *Blender* 3D creation suite [39], exposing its rendering engine through a standardized HDP interface.

5.3.1 Specification and Interface Congruency

The `component.yaml` file acts as the binding contract, defining the component's interface independently of its underlying technology. It declares a required input `input_dir` for raw 3D models and an `output_dir` for the generated imagery. Crucially, it abstracts complex rendering parameters into user-friendly controls. For

¹<https://zenodo.org/communities/hdp-components/>

instance, the `quality` parameter offers presets ("draft", "medium", "ultra") which map to specific internal sample rates and resolutions.

The interface layer (`main.py`) ensures strict congruency with this specification. Using the `argparse` library [40], it maps every parameter defined in the YAML, such as `--light-energy` or `--camera-dist`, to executable arguments. This layer also handles infrastructure-level logic that lies outside the core processing scope. For the Fast Renderer, this includes a portable GPU detection routine (`detect_available_gpus`) that inspects the host environment for NVIDIA or Apple Metal accelerators to optimize resource allocation.

5.3.2 Metaprogramming in the Logic Layer

The core logic layer (`processor.py`) demonstrates the power of the HDP's encapsulation strategy. Rather than interacting with Blender's API directly (which would require the HDP to run within Blender's embedded Python environment), the `OptimizedRendererProcessor` class employs a metaprogramming approach.

The processor utilizes a string template, `OPTIMIZED_BATCH_TEMPLATE`, to dynamically generate a dedicated Python script at runtime. This script injects the user-defined parameters, such as resolution, lighting angles, and engine selection, directly into the Blender context. The processor then orchestrates the execution via the `subprocess` module, streaming the standard output in real-time to capture distinct `BATCH_LOG` signals. This separation ensures that the HDP's dependency environment remains isolated from the strict requirement sets of external tools like Blender, preventing library conflicts while maintaining full control over the execution lifecycle.

5.4 Component Implementation Case Study: The LLM Processor

While the Fast Renderer demonstrates deterministic media processing, the *LLM Processor* component illustrates how the HDP architecture manages the probabilistic nature of Generative AI. This component is designed to extract structured metadata from unstructured text or tabular data using local LLMs via the *Ollama* framework.

5.4.1 Interface Polymorphism

The interface layer (`main.py`) of this component handles input polymorphism. The `component.yaml` specification defines two mutually exclusive data inputs: a simple string (`input_text`) and a file path (`table_file_path`) for batch processing CSV or Excel datasets. The CLI wrapper logic parses these arguments to determine the execution mode. In *Table Mode*, it utilizes the `table_column_mapping` parameter to dynamically inject row values into prompt placeholders, such as mapping a "Bio" column to a `biography` variable. This effectively treats the LLM as a row-by-row transformation engine.

5.4.2 Logic Layer: Validation and Self-Correction

The core challenges of integrating LLMs into scientific pipelines are hallucination and structural inconsistency. The `LLMProcessor` class addresses this through a rigorous "Generate-Repair-Validate" cycle implemented in the logic layer. Instead of accepting raw model output, the processor enforces a `json_schema` constraint. The execution flow, managed by the `_run_llm` method, proceeds as follows:

1. **Generation:** The system formats a prompt using the `PromptStore`, which decouples prompt engineering from code, and queries the local Ollama instance.
2. **Repair:** A heuristic `attempt_json_repair` utility strips Markdown code fences (e.g., ````json`) and fixes common syntax errors, such as trailing commas, which frequently occur with smaller models.
3. **Validation and Fallback:** The result is validated against the defined schema. Uniquely, if validation fails, the component can trigger a `fallback_prompt_key` (e.g., a "final" attempt with stricter instructions) to auto-correct the output before flagging it as a failure.

5.4.3 AI Provenance and Paradata

To satisfy transparency requirements and processing provenance, the component implements comprehensive paradata logging. The output JSON does not merely contain the extracted results; it includes a `paradata` object recording the exact `execution_start` time, the specific `model` version used (e.g., "qwen3:8b"), and crucially, the full text of the system and user prompt templates employed during the run. This ensures that AI-derived metadata remains auditable and reproducible.

5.5 Execution and Orchestration

The orchestration of these components is managed by the `component_runner_api`, which handles the lifecycle of execution, resource allocation, and status monitoring.

5.5.1 Asynchronous Execution

When a component is triggered, the system initiates an asynchronous execution process, returning a unique UUID (Universally Unique Identifier, Version 4) [41] to track the instance. This identifier allows the frontend to query the execution state (transitioning through `Running`, `Completed`, or `Failed` statuses) without blocking the main application thread. The runner utility constructs the specific shell command by inspecting the component's CLI patterns (e.g., detecting support for `--output-dir` versus `--output-file` flags) and resolving absolute file paths.

5.5.2 Real-Time Monitoring via SSE

To provide immediate feedback to the user, HDP implements Server-Sent Events (SSE). The `/components/logs/<execution_id>` endpoint opens a unidirectional stream that pushes log messages (categorized as `info`, `warning`, or `error`) from the Python subprocess directly to the user interface in real-time. This mechanism includes heartbeat signals to maintain connection stability during long-running processes.

5.5.3 Environment Isolation

A critical feature of the HDP is its resolution of dependency conflicts. The system leverages `uv` to manage distinct virtual environments for each component. The runner dynamically resolves the Python executable path within the specific component's environment (e.g., looking into `env/bin` on Unix or `env/Scripts` on Windows). This ensures that a component requiring legacy libraries can coexist in the same pipeline as one utilizing cutting-edge dependencies.

5.6 Pipeline Construction and Logic

Pipelines in HDP are defined not merely as ordered lists of tasks, but as complex, serialized structures that handle data flow and metadata transformation.

5.6.1 Step-wise Execution and Serialization

Pipelines are defined as YAML files and database representations where each element represents a processing step containing a `component_name`, `parameters`, and an `inputMapping` configuration. The input mapping logic resolves dependencies dynamically; for instance, an input for Step 2 can be explicitly mapped to the output of Step 1 using a `sourceType: pipelineFile` reference. This allows for the construction of non-linear workflows where intermediate derivatives are passed between isolated components. A typical use case of this principle is executing geolocalization components on photographs, and mapping the resulting coordinates to linked data carriers such as IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) manifest files [42] or Europeana Data Model (EDM) XMLs [43].

5.6.2 Metadata Overrides and Injection

A powerful capability of the pipeline engine is the programmatic extraction and injection of metadata. Pipeline steps can be configured with an `outputMapping`, which instructs the system to parse the JSON output of a component and map specific keys to Zenodo metadata fields.

For example, a "Metadata Extractor" component might analyze an FITS [44] image header and output a JSON file containing technical metadata. The pipeline manager can be configured to extract this specific data and inject it into the `description` or `keywords` fields of the target Zenodo record. This mechanism effectively overrides the initial, static metadata mapping derived from the spreadsheet, allowing for data-driven, automated enrichment of the final archival record.

5.7 High-Performance Computing (HPC) Integration

To accommodate the computational demands of modern heritage data processing, such as large-scale photogrammetry or AI-driven geolocation, the HDP architecture incorporates a specialized `hpc-connector` module. Although currently implemented and validated within test environments, this middleware is scheduled for public release in subsequent updates. It mediates the interaction between the local HDP instance and remote supercomputing clusters, functionally integrating an HPC node as an ephemeral extension of the local pipeline.

5.7.1 Remote Orchestration Architecture

The integration utilizes a lightweight client-side orchestrator (`hpc_orchestrator.py`) that manages the lifecycle of a remote job without requiring a persistent server agent on the cluster. The workflow adheres to a strict execution sequence:

1. **Dynamic Allocation:** The system connects to a defined SSH gateway (e.g., `draco`) and requests resources via the Slurm Workload Manager using `salloc`. It employs a state tracker to monitor the transition from `PENDING` to `READY`, parsing real-time standard output (`stdout`) streams to identify the allocated node (e.g., `gpu01`).
2. **Data Synchronization:** Upon node allocation, the connector utilizes `rsync` over SSH to transfer input assets from the local project to the remote workspace. This ensures that only necessary data is transferred, thereby optimizing bandwidth usage.
3. **Wrapper-Based Execution:** To maintain compatibility with the HDP component standard, remote tools are wrapped in a specialized CLI script (e.g., `hdp_cli.py`). This wrapper standardizes argument parsing and ensures that the remote application accepts inputs and produces outputs in a format congruent with local pipeline definitions.
4. **Result Retrieval and Cleanup:** Upon successful execution (detected via configurable success indicators in the log stream), results are synchronized back to the local output directory, and temporary remote files are purged to maintain cluster hygiene.

5.7.2 Profile-Based Configuration

The complexity of heterogeneous cluster environments is abstracted through a centralized `config.json` file. This file defines "Resource Profiles" (e.g., `gpu_large`, `testgpu_quick`) that map to specific Slurm partition and memory configurations, as well as *CUDA Profiles* that handle the loading of environment modules and library paths. This decoupling enables the HDP to adapt to disparate HPC infrastructures solely through configuration updates, avoiding alterations to the core codebase.

6 Repository Integration and Publication Lifecycle

The primary objective of the HDP is the reliable, automated publication of data to persistent repositories. To achieve this, the system implements a deterministic state machine that governs the transition of digital objects from local storage to the Zenodo infrastructure, ensuring transactional integrity across the publication lifecycle.

6.1 The Zenodo Workflow State Machine

The HDP workflow is designed as a strict state machine, transitioning records through distinct phases: *Preparation*, *Draft Management*, and *Publication*.

6.1.1 Preparation Phase

The lifecycle commences with the transition from raw file processing to internal database preparation. Upon the execution of the metadata mapping, the system validates the extracted metadata against the Zenodo JSON schema. Validated records are stored in the local `zenodo_records` table with a status of `prepared`. This internal staging area allows researchers to review and refine metadata locally (applying manual overrides or pipeline-derived enrichments) without interacting with external APIs or consuming network resources.

6.1.2 Draft Management and Environments

Once prepared, records transition to the *Draft* state through interaction with the Zenodo API. The HDP architecture strictly enforces environment separation, utilizing distinct API credentials for the **Sandbox** (testing) and **Production** (live) environments. When a draft is instantiated via the `create_api_draft` endpoint, the system retrieves the remote Deposition ID and pre-reserves the DOI, binding them to the local record. This allows researchers to embed the persistent identifier into their data during runtime, such as linked data XML files, prior to the final upload. In practice, this capability is utilized to self-reference the record's version within descriptions (e.g., changelogs) and, specifically, to generate and upload XML files compliant with the Europeana Data Model (EDM) [see 43].

6.1.3 Versioning Logic

A critical component of the lifecycle is the automated management of versioning. Zenodo utilizes a *Concept DOI* to represent all versions of a dataset, while specific *Version DOIs* identify individual snapshots. HDP automates this complexity through the `create_new_version_draft` function. When updating a published record, the system queries the Concept ID to identify the latest version and automatically calculates the next semantic version number (defaulting to a patch increment, e.g., `v1.0.0` to `v1.0.1`, with user overrides for minor or major updates) before creating the new draft. This ensures citation continuity without manual intervention.

6.2 API Interaction and Fault Tolerance

Given the constraints of external web services, HDP incorporates robust fault tolerance mechanisms to handle network instability and API limitations.

6.2.1 Rate Limiting

To maintain compliance with Zenodo's usage policies, all outgoing requests are mediated by an internal `rate_limiter_zenodo` service. This middleware enforces a mandated wait time between requests, preventing the application from triggering "429 Too Many Requests" errors during bulk operations.

6.2.2 Error Recovery: Discard and Restore

Draft operations can fail due to various external factors, leaving the local database out of synchronization with the remote repository. HDP implements a "Discard and Restore" pattern to mitigate this risk via the `discard_zenodo_draft` endpoint.

Before any destructive API call, the system creates a snapshot in the `metadata_backups` table. If a draft requires discarding, whether due to user request or API failure, the system not only sends the delete command to Zenodo but also invokes the `_restore_record_metadata` routine. This function rolls back the local record state to its pre-draft configuration, restoring denormalized fields and clearing invalid IDs, effectively reversing the failed operation.

6.2.3 Mitigating Repository Retrieval Limits

A significant architectural limitation of the Zenodo API is the retrieval cap of 10,000 records. While heuristic strategies like sorting inversion can extend this to 20,000, it leaves an informational gap for collections exceeding this size, preventing efficient synchronization via API calls alone. HDP circumvents this by treating the local `.hdp` database (rather than the remote repository) as the source of truth. By persisting the link between local assets and Zenodo Deposit IDs internally, the system eliminates the need to fetch the full deposit list from the API. This allows HDP to manage collections of arbitrary size (e.g., exceeding 50,000 items) while circumventing retrieval ceilings and pagination bottlenecks.

6.3 Batch Processing Capabilities

To support institutional-scale digitization, HDP exposes a `batch_actions_api` capable of executing lifecycle transitions on large-scale datasets simultaneously.

This API supports bulk operations for every stage of the workflow: `prepare_metadata`, `create_api_draft`, `upload_main_files`, and `publish`. To mitigate the inherent instability of network operations during long-running tasks, the batch processor implements a robust auto-retry mechanism with exponential backoff. When a transient error occurs (such as a 503 Service Unavailable or a network timeout), the system does not immediately mark the record as failed. Instead, it pauses execution for a calculated interval (base delay of 2s, increasing exponentially up to 30s) and retries the operation up to three times. This ensures that temporary API instabilities do not disrupt overnight ingestion workflows.

Furthermore, the processor employs a "Multi-Status" error handling strategy, analogous to HTTP 207. If retries are exhausted and a definitive failure occurs, the system isolates the exception to the specific record. The process continues for all remaining items, and the final response provides a granular report detailing which IDs succeeded and which failed, along with specific error diagnostics. This capability allows operators to address only the problematic entries without the necessity of restarting the entire batch operation.

7 Interfaces and Extensibility

While the GUI lowers the barrier to entry for users, the HDP architecture acknowledges that large-scale data engineering requires automation, reproducibility, and headless operation. To satisfy these requirements, the system exposes its functionality through two primary programmatic interfaces: a comprehensive CLI and a structured REST API.

7.1 User Stability and Feature Gating

To maintain a robust user experience for non-experts, HDP implements a strict feature-gating middleware, the *Feature Stability Gate*. Recognizing that experimental features can compromise data integrity or confuse users, this system selectively disables UI elements (such as specific buttons or navigation views like *Storage*

Optimization or *Pipeline View*) that are currently flagged as work-in-progress. Crucially, this blocking logic applies strictly to the GUI to prevent accidental misuse. The functionalities remain fully accessible via the CLI and API, allowing developers and power users to utilize and test alpha features programmatically without exposing general users to instability.

7.2 Graphical User Interface Modules

While the backend manages data integrity, the Electron-based frontend translates these abstract architectures into a visual workspace designed for non-technical users. This interface is organized into distinct modules that expose the system’s logic through interactive visual paradigms.

7.2.1 The Pipeline Constructor Interface

The *Pipeline Constructor* serves as a visual programming environment that abstracts the JSON-based pipeline definitions described in subsection 5.6. Unlike linear script editors, this view renders the processing workflow as a sequential series of *Step Blocks*, each representing a discrete processing unit.

- **Visual Data Flow:** The interface implements a *File Card* system where input and output assets are represented as manipulatable UI objects. Users configure data flow not by writing paths, but by selecting file cards generated by previous steps using a dynamic input selector.
- **Metadata Injection Logic:** A dedicated *Initial Step* block allows for the global configuration of the Zenodo draft. Subsequent steps feature an *Output Mapping* modal where users can visually map specific component outputs (e.g., a JSON log file) to Zenodo metadata fields, with the UI creating visual flags (e.g., "Overwrites Metadata") to warn users of data precedence conflicts.
- **Description Templating:** The module includes a *Description Constructor* step that utilizes a variable-based templating system (e.g., `#{output_file.coordinates.x}`), allowing the final description to be dynamically generated from the analytical results of the pipeline.

7.2.2 The Component Repository

To manage the modular ecosystem, the GUI includes the *Component Repository*. Surpassing a static enumeration, this interface acts as a real-time dashboard for the local component library.

- **Categorized Management:** Components are organized into collapsible categories (e.g., "3D Processing", "Metadata Extraction") with visual status indicators distinguishing between "Installed", "Available", and "Invalid" states.
- **Update Management:** The view integrates with the remote registry to perform version checks. An *Available Updates* modal allows users to compare local versus remote versions and view changelogs rendered directly from the remote repository’s Markdown files before authorizing an update.
- **Online Discovery:** A *Download Components* interface queries the central registry for new modules, allowing users to expand their processing capabilities without leaving the application context.

7.2.3 Interactive Component Execution and Testing

Recognizing that pipelines are complex to debug, the HDP includes a *Component Execution* interface that functions as an interactive unit-testing ground. Accessible via the *Run* button on any installed component, this modal allows users to execute a processor in isolation.

- **Dynamic Parameterization:** The interface dynamically generates form controls based on the component’s YAML specification, rendering file pickers for `path` types, toggle switches for `boolean` flags, and dropdowns for `enums`.

- **Template System:** To facilitate repetitive testing, the manager supports a *Parameter Template* system, allowing users to save and load specific configuration sets (e.g., "High-Res Photogrammetry Settings") for rapid reuse.
- **Real-Time Feedback:** Execution logs are streamed in real-time via SSE to a dedicated console window, allowing operators to diagnose failures or verify outputs immediately without inspecting backend log files.

7.2.4 Automated Installation Wizard

The installation of complex research software is streamlined through the *Component Installation Manager*. This wizard abstracts the underlying uv environment provisioning into a guided graphical process.

- **Pre-Flight Validation:** Before installation begins, the manager parses the component's requirements to perform system checks (e.g., verifying GPU availability or Python versions).
- **Dependency Resolution:** It visualizes the requirement for auxiliary files (such as machine learning model weights or binaries), providing direct download links and validation logic to ensure all dependencies are present before the environment is built.

7.2.5 The Dashboard and Upload Manager

The publication lifecycle state machine is visualized through the *Upload Manager*. This view replaces the abstract concept of database states with a tabbed interface ("Pending Preparation", "Drafts", "Published"), allowing users to promote records through the preservation lifecycle via action buttons. It includes a real-time *Dashboard* that aggregates project statistics (such as total file count, record distribution across environments, and metadata completion rates), providing immediate visual feedback on the project's archival readiness.

7.3 The Command-Line Interface (CLI)

The HDP CLI serves as an orchestration tool designed for server-side environments and automated workflows, effectively decoupling the processing logic from the Electron-based frontend.

7.3.1 Headless Operation

The CLI exposes the entire preservation lifecycle through a suite of `hdp` commands, enabling operations on headless servers where a GUI is unavailable by default.

- `hdp upload`: This command automates the ingestion process by scanning a specified input directory, registering files in the `.hdpc` database, executing metadata preparation logic, and instantiating Zenodo drafts in the target environment (Sandbox or Production).
- `hdp process`: This command triggers pipeline execution on existing records. It supports granular filtering options (such as `--since`, `--until`, or `--title-pattern`), allowing operators to target specific subsets of data for transformation (e.g., processing only records created in the last 24 hours).
- `hdp publish`: Representing the final step in the lifecycle, this command validates that all file uploads are complete and commits the drafts to the repository, making them publicly accessible via DOI.

7.3.2 Daemon Management

To facilitate integration into system services or Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines, the CLI implements an automatic daemon management strategy. When an `hdp` command is issued, the tool checks for an active instance of the backend server. If none is detected, it automatically spawns the `hdp-server` process to handle the request and manages its lifecycle, thereby eliminating the need for

manual server startup. Conversely, advanced users can utilize the `--no-auto-server` flag to interface with an existing, long-running server instance.

7.4 REST API Design

Underlying both the Electron GUI and the CLI is a RESTful API architecture built on the Flask framework. This API is segmented into logical namespaces that reflect the resource-oriented nature of the application.

7.4.1 API Structure Overview

The API surface is organized into distinct blueprints to enforce a separation of concerns:

- `/project`: Endpoints under this namespace manage the project state, handling file scanning, database persistence, and metadata preparation routines.
- `/pipelines`: This controller manages the definition, Create/Read/Update/Delete (CRUD) operations, and execution of processing pipelines. It handles the serialization of pipeline steps and the mapping of input/output artifacts between components.
- `/pipeline_components`: Dedicated to the component ecosystem, these endpoints facilitate the discovery, installation, and configuration of modular processors. They also expose health check and storage optimization routines.
- `/zenodo`: These endpoints abstract the complexity of the external Zenodo API, providing simplified methods for record retrieval and file synchronization (often integrated within project routes).

7.4.2 The CLI Routes API

A distinctive feature of the HDP architecture is the `cli_routes_api (/cli)`, designed specifically to support robust batch scripting. Recognizing that GUI-driven endpoints often include logic for user feedback (e.g., flash messages) or single-item error blocking, the CLI routes are engineered for fault tolerance.

For example, the `/cli/pipelines/<name>/execute` endpoint implements a "Multi-Status" response pattern (HTTP 207). Instead of halting a batch operation upon a single record failure (a scenario catastrophic in long-running automated tasks), this endpoint isolates exceptions. It processes the entire list of provided record IDs and returns a comprehensive report detailing successful transactions alongside specific error messages for failed items, enabling retry logic without manual intervention.

7.5 WebHDP: The Server-Hosted Browser Interface

Complementing the Electron desktop client and the CLI, **WebHDP** represents the third component of the system's interface strategy. Currently in active development and successfully validated in internal trials, WebHDP transforms the HDP from a single-user local tool into a centralized, multi-user platform suitable for institutional deployment.

7.5.1 Microservice Architecture and Stack

WebHDP is architected as a containerized microservice ecosystem orchestrated via Docker Compose.

- **Reactive Frontend**: The user interface is a Single Page Application (SPA) built with **Vue 3** [45] and **Vite** [46], utilizing **Pinia** [47] for state management and **Tailwind CSS** [12] for responsive design. Unlike the desktop version, this frontend is completely decoupled from the file system, interacting solely via HTTP requests.
- **Orchestration Backend**: A dedicated Flask application (`web`) serves as the middleware layer. It manages user authentication using JSON Web Tokens (JWT) [48], session persistence, and database

state via **SQLAlchemy** [49]. Crucially, this backend does not reimplement core processing logic; instead, it acts as a proxy that instantiates and controls project sessions, relaying computationally intensive tasks (such as scanning and pipeline execution) to the isolated **HDP API** container (`hdp-api`).

7.5.2 Multi-User Collaboration and Role-Based Access Control (RBAC)

A significant advancement over the desktop client is the introduction of rigorous user management. The system implements Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) defining three distinct privileges: *Users* (upload and process), *Moderators* (review submissions), and *Admins* (system configuration).

The workflow introduces a *Submission* lifecycle:

1. **Session Isolation:** Users upload files into isolated temporary workspaces managed by the `SessionManager`, ensuring data privacy between concurrent users.
2. **Dynamic Metadata Entry:** The upload interface renders dynamic metadata forms driven by a server-side JSON schema (`zenodo_metadata_schema.json`), enforcing validation rules before processing begins.
3. **Moderation Queue:** Submitted datasets enter a review queue where Moderators can inspect metadata, view processing results, and approve or request revisions before final publication.

7.5.3 Security and Deployment

Designed for server deployment, WebHDP incorporates security measures absent in the local version. A `SecurityValidator` module enforces strict path sanitization to prevent directory traversal attacks during file operations. The application routes are protected by JWTs, and file uploads are validated against strict MIME-type and extension allowlist configurations.

8 Evaluation and Case Studies

8.1 3D Heritage Workflow Case Study

A prevalent challenge in 3D digitization is the complex file dependency structure inherent to formats such as Wavefront OBJ. It is rare for complex digital artifacts to exist as individual files; they are usually constituted of aggregated entities. For instance, a standard 3D model consists of a geometry mesh (`.obj`), a material definition library (`.mtl`), and multiple high-resolution texture maps (e.g., `.jpg`, `.png`), often organized within subdirectory structures. Preserving the semantic link between these files is critical for the object's future renderability.

In this case study, we utilize the HDP's *Subdirectory Mode* to process a collection of photogrammetric models from an archaeological site. The input directory is structured such that each artifact resides in a distinct, named folder (e.g., `/SiteA/Artifact_01/`), containing the model files and a `textures` subdirectory.

Upon initialization, the HDP scanner identifies each subdirectory as a distinct *Record*. Using the 3D Model modality template, the system automatically parses the `.obj` files to identify their dependent `.mtl` libraries. Furthermore, it parses the `.mtl` files to locate referenced texture maps.

A specific optimization feature employed here is the `archive_subdirectories` option. Zenodo, in common with many repositories, imposes soft limits on the number of individual files per deposit to ensure efficient indexing. To adhere to these best practices without manual intervention, the HDP scanner detects the `textures` subfolder and automatically compresses it into a ZIP archive (e.g., `Artifact_01_textures.zip`). This archive is then registered in the file hierarchy as a child of the primary model, maintaining the logical relationship while significantly reducing the file count for the final deposition.

8.2 Performance of Distributed Rendering

The "Fast Renderer" component provides a distinct case study for analyzing the performance impact of the HDP's hybrid parallelization strategy. In contrast to traditional heritage workflows that often rely on serial execution, this component implements a two-tiered concurrency model designed to maximize throughput on heterogeneous cluster architectures.

8.2.1 Hybrid Parallelization Strategy

The first tier operates at the cluster level through the `hpc-mode` parameter. By detecting environment variables such as `SLURM_ARRAY_TASK_ID`, the component automatically identifies its position within a distributed job array. Instead of requiring a central manager to dispatch individual tasks (a process prone to creating network bottlenecks), each instance autonomously calculates its specific data chunk (e.g., models 1–50 of 1000) based on its array index and the total chunk count. This "shared-nothing" architecture minimizes inter-node communication overhead, a critical factor when scaling to multiple nodes.

The second tier addresses intra-node performance. The component's orchestration layer (`main.py`) interrogates the local hardware topology via `nvidia-smi` to detect available GPU accelerators. Unlike basic script execution, which might leave resources idle, the renderer spawns a `ProcessPoolExecutor` matched to the number of detected GPUs. It explicitly binds each worker process to a specific device via the `CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES` environment variable, ensuring that a multi-GPU node (e.g., a server with 4x NVIDIA A100 GPUs) is fully saturated.

8.2.2 Throughput and Overhead

This architecture significantly reduces the "wall-time" for large-scale digitization projects. By handling the rendering logic within a persistent Python process that spawns Blender subprocesses only as needed, the component amortizes the initialization cost of the Python interpreter. However, the implementation also necessitates a trade-off: the `timeout-multiplier` parameter implies a requirement for strict process management to prevent "zombie" processes in distributed environments, where a single stalled render could otherwise impede an entire job array. The implementation of a "soft" timeout within the Python wrapper, prior to the hard system kill signal, ensures that partial results from a batch can be preserved even if specific models fail, thereby enhancing the overall resilience of the preservation pipeline.

8.3 Deployment and Validation in Research Infrastructures

The architectural resilience and practical utility of the HDP have been validated through its deployment in multiple high-impact European research initiatives. The system's developmental origins lie in the *INDUX-R Project: Industrial Research and Innovation for Cultural Heritage* [50], where early iterations of the batch-processing logic were evaluated against large and diverse quantities of heritage datasets (exceeding 100,000 records). These foundational workflows were subsequently refined and expanded within the scope of the *3DBigDataSpace Project* [51], which necessitated the handling of the significantly larger, heterogeneous datasets typical of transnational digitization efforts. Additionally, the architectural predecessor was employed to facilitate the automated publication of the *musiXplora* knowledge base's [52] subset of musical instrument builders (9,100 records),² ensuring the persistent accessibility of complex structured musicological and organological data on the Zenodo repository [see 53].

Significantly, HDP functions as the central data management backbone for the *MODAVIS* project (Multimodal Organological Data Analysis and Virtualization Systems). In this context, the system orchestrates the "Large-Scale Georeferenced 3D Reconstruction of Pipe Organs," managing the complex interdependencies between point clouds, organological and acoustical data representations, related identifiers, and geospatial metadata

²<https://zenodo.org/communities/digital-organology/>

[54]. This deployment specifically leverages the HDP’s multimodal templates and component-based rendering pipelines to process multi-source heritage data into FAIR-compliant archival records, demonstrating the system’s capacity to facilitate the transition between raw data acquisition and long-term preservation in interdisciplinary research.

9 Discussion: Ethics, Standards, and Governance

Having established the technical efficacy of the system, the subsequent discussion will address the theoretical and ethical implications of the HDP architecture. This section evaluates the system’s alignment with the FAIR principles, analyzes the legal and infrastructural realities of the Zenodo repository, and discusses the ethical responsibilities inherent in the automation of cultural heritage digitization.

9.1 FAIR Compliance Assessment

The HDP architecture is engineered to operationalize the FAIR guiding principles not only for the digital heritage data it processes but also for the computational workflows it executes. This dual compliance is critical, as workflows act as the *process description* that ensures data reproducibility. We map the system’s features to the foundational principles as defined for data by Jacobsen et al. [29] and adapted for computational workflows by Wilkinson et al. [55].

9.1.1 Findability (F): PIDs and Rich Metadata

Principle F1 requires the assignment of globally unique and persistent identifiers (PIDs). HDP automates this by pre-reserving DOIs via the Zenodo API during the *Draft* stage, binding the local record to a persistent identifier before publication. In the context of workflows, HDP addresses the requirement that “components of the workflow representing levels of granularity are assigned distinct identifiers” (F1.1) through the Component Registry, which assigns unique IDs and version tags to individual processing modules [55]. Furthermore, the Metadata Mapping Wizard addresses principle F2 (Rich Metadata) by enforcing the population of mandatory fields to support machine-actionability [29, p. 15]. By registering these records in Zenodo, HDP ensures that the metadata remains indexed and searchable (F4), even if the data files are restricted.

9.1.2 Accessibility (A): Protocol Standardization

HDP relies on the HTTPS protocol via the Zenodo API for all data transmission, satisfying principle A1 which calls for open, free, and universally implementable communication protocols [29, p. 18]. The system’s authentication handler, which manages personal access tokens securely, aligns with principle A1.2, allowing for authentication and authorization procedures where necessary. Crucially, by separating metadata uploads from file uploads, HDP supports principle A2. As noted by Wilkinson et al. [55, p. 4], for workflows, this implies that the “workflow description” (metadata) must remain accessible even if the executable software or infrastructure becomes unavailable.

9.1.3 Interoperability (I): Modular Specifications

Interoperability in computational workflows requires that components can exchange data via domain-relevant standards (I3). HDP enforces this through the `component.yaml` specification layer. This file acts as a formal knowledge representation (I1), rigorously defining input and output MIME types to prevent pipeline mismatches. Furthermore, the integration of the Metadata Wizard with controlled vocabularies (e.g., resource types, license URIs) ensures that the output metadata adheres to shared vocabularies (I2), preventing the ambiguity that leads to false agreements” or false disagreements” in machine interpretation [29, p. 22].

9.1.4 Reusability (R): Provenance and State Persistence

The primary goal of FAIR is reuse, which requires detailed provenance (R1.2). In the context of workflows, this necessitates capturing the *Workflow Run* (the instantiation of a workflow with specific inputs and parameters) as distinct from the *Workflow Specification* [55, p. 2]. The HDP's `.hdpc` SQLite database functions as this provenance container (R1.3). It records the exact version of every HDP Component used, the parameter settings applied, and the execution logs, ensuring that the processing history is not lost upon publication. In addition, each component can be identified, retrieved and reused, as they are accessible on Zenodo via their corresponding DOI. Finally, the `metadata_mapping` module mandates the selection of a license (R1.1), ensuring that both the data and the associated metadata have clear usage conditions [29, p. 24].

9.2 Reproducibility and Standards

The pervasive challenge of reproducibility in computational research extends significantly to data preservation pipelines. Reliance on ad-hoc scripts frequently introduces dependencies on implicit environment variables or unversioned libraries, thereby impeding the replication of processing workflows across institutional boundaries. HDP addresses this systemic issue through the dual standardization of project state and processing logic.

9.2.1 The Portable Project State (`.hdpc`)

The `.hdpc` database file functions as a persistent and portable record of the preservation process. By encapsulating the file inventory alongside exact metadata mappings, pipeline configurations, and complete processing history, it enables the asynchronous suspension, transfer, and resumption of projects across disparate computing environments without loss of context. This portability ensures that the curatorial intent of the operator (specifically regarding file grouping logic and metadata derivation strategies) is preserved alongside the raw data.

9.2.2 Component Specification (`component.yaml`)

Reproducibility at the algorithmic level is strictly enforced via the `component.yaml` specification. By rigorously defining input/output contracts and, crucially, pinning the exact versions of Python packages and system dependencies (e.g., `ffmpeg >= 4.0`), the system guarantees that pipeline components exhibit deterministic behavior across heterogeneous environments. The integration of `uv` to provision isolated, specification-compliant virtual environments mitigates the "dependency drift" that frequently undermines long-term software stability. This architecture ensures longitudinal consistency, guaranteeing that a geometry conversion pipeline executed in the future yields results identical to the initial run.

9.3 Repository Suitability and Policy

The selection of Zenodo as the primary target repository for the HDP is predicated not merely on its openness, but on a critical assessment of its infrastructural permanence and legal frameworks. However, reliance on this infrastructure necessitates a clear understanding of the shared responsibility model imposed by CERN's governance, a necessity underscored by recent evaluations of risks and trust in persistent identifier infrastructures [56].

To ensure the long-term viability of the preservation workflow, the HDP architecture must be evaluated not only on technical merit but on its strict adherence to the Zenodo Terms of Use and operational policies. Non-compliance poses a risk of account suspension or IP blocking, which would disrupt institutional digitization efforts.

9.3.1 Infrastructural Permanence and Data Integrity

Zenodo is hosted by CERN, utilizing the organization’s High Energy Physics (HEP) infrastructure to ensure long-term preservation of research data. The physical layer relies on the CERN Data Centre’s EOS service, a disk cluster currently exceeding 5 PB for Zenodo specifically [57]. To mitigate bit-rot, a critical concern for digital heritage assets such as high-resolution photogrammetry, the system employs a dual-checksum strategy. One MD5 checksum is managed by the InvenioRDM software layer to detect external changes, while a second independent checksum is maintained by the EOS storage layer for low-level corruption recovery [57]. Furthermore, data redundancy is enforced through daily incremental backups to a Ceph cluster located in a geographically distinct facility [57]. This robust architecture contributes to the significant socio-economic value of the platform, estimated at nearly 2.8 billion CHF in potential impact over a thirty-year horizon [58].

9.3.2 Legal Framework and GDPR Alignment

For institutional users of the HDP, the legal status of the repository is of paramount importance. CERN operates as an Intergovernmental Organization (IGO) with legal personality and immunity from national jurisdiction [57]. Consequently, Zenodo is not directly subject to the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Instead, personal data processing is governed by CERN’s *Operational Circular 11* (OC11), which aligns with GDPR principles but operates under international law [59].

This distinction creates a specific compliance constraint for HDP workflows: CERN explicitly states that it cannot execute Data Processing Agreements (DPAs) with individual institutions [59]. Therefore, the HDP architecture places the burden of data sovereignty on the local pre-processing stage. Since the repository cannot serve as a legal data processor under a DPA, the HDP complies with these constraints through its “Local-First” architecture. By enforcing data processing within the local environment, the system acts as a sanitization layer. The `exclusion_filters` and `metadata_cleaning` modules allow users to retain sensitive information locally while publishing only the sanitized subsets. This functionality directly addresses Zenodo’s policy advice that uploaders considering the storage of “un anonymised or encrypted/unencrypted sensitive personal data are advised to use bespoke platforms rather than open dissemination services” [59, 60].

9.3.3 The Limitations of Closed Access

While Zenodo supports “Closed Access” and “Restricted Access” modalities, the HDP documentation must explicitly warn users against utilizing these features for sensitive cultural heritage data (e.g., locations of looting-prone sites or unreleased indigenous knowledge). The infrastructure policy explicitly clarifies that “closed” files are stored unencrypted and remain accessible to operational staff [57]. Consequently, the Terms of Use stipulate that the platform is unsuitable for confidential data [60]. This necessitates that the HDP’s encryption or redaction must occur locally (client-side) before ingestion, as the repository’s access controls are logical rather than cryptographic. Such precautions are vital given that trust in PID infrastructures relies heavily on transparent risk assessment regarding data immutability and access control [56].

9.3.4 Liability and Licensing

The operational model of Zenodo enforces a strict indemnification clause, holding the uploader exclusively responsible for all content and copyright clearance [60]. This reinforces the necessity of the HDP’s `metadata_mapping`, validation modules, and potentially further mechanisms to prevent critical infringements. By automating the assignment of licenses and ensuring consistent attribution in the metadata schemas, HDP assists users in complying with the requirement that all uploaded content must be suitable for open dissemination and free of intellectual property violations [60]. Furthermore, users must be aware that while they retain ownership of the data, the descriptive metadata submitted to Zenodo is released under a CC0 waiver to facilitate interoperability [60].

Additionally, the platform is designated for research outputs, with specific policies noting that items such

as Curricula Vitae (CVs) are not considered “product/output of a research process” and are thus outside the scope of Zenodo [59]. The HDP is capable to facilitate compliance with these terms via the Modality Templates. By enforcing strict file extension presets that limit valid inputs to formats intrinsic to the selected research domain (e.g., limiting the *3D Model* modality to geometry and texture extensions), the system effectively acts as a filter, preventing the inadvertent upload of administrative or personal documents, which do not conform to the authorized allowlists. Furthermore, the Metadata Mapping Wizard integrates controlled vocabularies to ensure that license definitions are explicit, aiding the user in fulfilling their responsibility to respect applicable license conditions [60].

9.3.5 The Limits of Passive Persistence: Bit-Level vs. Functional Preservation

While Zenodo provides robust infrastructural security, a critical distinction must be drawn between *bit-level preservation* and *functional preservation*. As a generalist repository, Zenodo operates primarily as a “passive” archive; it guarantees the bitwise integrity of the uploaded file through redundancy and checksums, ensuring that the digital object retrieved in twenty years is identical to the one deposited today [61]. However, it does not perform *active preservation* or format migration, making no promises regarding the future usability or understandability of deposited objects [61].

This limitation is particularly acute for the heterogeneous heritage data processed by the HDP. Unlike simple text files, 3D formats (e.g., OBJ, PLY, GLB) and multispectral imaging data are highly susceptible to *functional obsolescence* [62]. A proprietary binary format secured on CERN’s servers may remain bit-perfect for decades while simultaneously becoming renderable by no extant software, effectively turning the repository into a “dark archive” [62]. Furthermore, without an associated information system to execute or visualize these data points, the mere persistence of the files fails to support actual decision-making or reuse, as users must download entire datasets to determine relevance [63].

Consequently, the *persistence factor* of the repository is intrinsically linked to the pre-ingestion standardization enforced by the HDP. By validating data against open, non-proprietary standards (e.g., enforcing ASCII-based OBJ over binary formats, or requesting PDF/A for documents) during the `scan` and `validation` phases, the HDP mitigates the risk of the repository becoming a graveyard of unreadable data. The user must recognize that Zenodo serves as the storage layer, but the *preservation strategy* remains the responsibility of the data producer. The HDP’s `.hdpc` project state facilitates this by allowing for the future re-hydration and potentially the batch-conversion of local assets if format standards shift, provided the local data is maintained alongside the remote deposit.

9.3.6 Comparative Analysis: Generalist vs. Domain-Specific Infrastructures

In evaluating Zenodo against alternative infrastructures, a clear dichotomy emerges between *generalist repositories* and *domain-specific platforms*. While Zenodo excels in bit-level permanence and FAIR compliance via automatic DOI minting, it is traditionally viewed as lacking the specialized visualization tools found in commercial platforms such as Sketchfab. This platform functions as a private viewer platform rather than a sustainable preservation repository, prioritizing user engagement and rendering quality over long-term archival guarantees [64, 65].

However, recent developments in 4D geo-modelling pipelines have bridged this viewer gap, demonstrating that Zenodo can effectively serve as a backend for external, real-time visualization applications. Münster et al. [66] successfully implemented a pipeline where large-scale 3D city models and building geometries (stored as glTF/GLB) are hosted on Zenodo to ensure long-term availability and citability, while being dynamically retrieved via API for display in browser-based applications. By leveraging Zenodo’s direct file links and predictable DOI versioning, external viewers (such as custom DFG 3D Viewer implementations [67] or the “4D Browser” [68]) can stream data directly from the repository without requiring the repository itself to render the content [66]. This effectively decouples the *storage layer* (Zenodo) from the *presentation layer* (external viewer), adhering to the modular design principles preferred for sustainable infrastructures.

Alternatively, domain-specific repositories such as MorphoSource [69] or tDAR [70] offer native, integrated handling of complex metadata and visualization [71]. These platforms support granular *active* preservation workflows, such as format migration and deep indexing, which Zenodo’s generic schema cannot match [71]. Yet, they often impose higher barriers to entry, including membership costs, whereas Zenodo’s inclusive approach allows for the rapid, cost-free deposit of heterogeneous datasets [58].

Therefore, the HDP’s strategic choice of Zenodo represents a compromise that no longer requires sacrificing visualization: it utilizes Zenodo for robust, citable storage [64] while enabling client-side or external visualization tools to consume the data directly [66]. This model aligns with the decoupled architecture where Zenodo acts as the permanent source for assets that can be integrated into dynamic frontend experiences.

9.3.7 API Usage and Operational Stability

While Zenodo offers robust archival capabilities, its operational constraints regarding API request limits and bandwidth usage make it unsuitable as a direct backend for live, high-frequency applications, positioning it instead as a persistent repository for digitized research artifacts. Moreover, Zenodo reserves the right to restrict or remove user access where it considers that use of the service “interferes with its operations” [60]. In practice, this often manifests as the blocking of IP addresses if an API client performs “an excessive amount of automated requests” which impacts service stability [59].

The HDP proactively addresses this operational risk through two specific mechanisms:

- **Client-Side Rate Limiting:** The internal `Rate Limiter` enforces a mandatory delay between requests, ensuring the client respects the repository’s stability requirements and avoids triggering 429 error blocks [59].
- **Pagination Avoidance:** By maintaining the file inventory and deposit IDs locally in `.hdpc` files, HDP minimizes the need to repeatedly query the Zenodo API for full deposit lists. This significantly reduces the request volume compared to standard API clients, aligning with the requirement to avoid interference with operations [60].

9.4 Ethical Governance: Integrating CARE Principles and Indigenous Data Sovereignty

While the HDP architecture emphasizes technical efficiency and adherence to the FAIR principles, the automated processing of cultural heritage data necessitates a rigorous ethical framework. Digitization is not a neutral technical act; it is a process of interpretation that can reinforce historical power imbalances or, conversely, serve as a tool for restitution and empowerment [72]. Consequently, the HDP workflow must be evaluated not only against technical metrics but also against the *CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance* (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics).

9.4.1 The Tension Between Open Data and Data Sovereignty

A central tension in modern digital preservation exists between the “open by default” ethos of repositories such as Zenodo and the rights of Indigenous peoples to control data about their communities, territories, and knowledge. Carroll et al. [73] argue that while the FAIR principles focus on data attributes (machine-readability and persistence), they fail to address the people and purposes behind the data.

The CARE principles address this deficit by prioritizing *Authority to Control*, ensuring that Indigenous rights and interests are recognized in governance protocols [73].

For HDP users, this distinction is critical. The system’s *Root Mode*’ or *Subdirectory Mode*’ scanning could inadvertently aggregate and publish sensitive data (such as sacred rituals or traditional ecological knowledge) that was never intended for public dissemination. Tsosie [74] emphasizes that *data sovereignty* is a foundational aspect of political self-determination, noting that tribal governments have an inherent right to govern the collection, ownership, and application of their data. This architecture supports the critical distinction

highlighted by Lovett et al. [75]: it provides the technical mechanisms for Indigenous *governance of data*, which is a prerequisite for mobilizing that *data for governance* and internal community decision-making. The uncritical upload of such data to open repositories, even under Restricted Access, may violate this sovereignty.

9.4.2 Mitigating Algorithmic Bias and "Data of Disregard"

The automation provided by HDP also carries the risk of amplifying "data of disregard," defined as data that frames Indigenous peoples solely through lenses of disparity or disadvantage, rather than nation-building or cultural resilience [72]. Manžuch [72] highlights that Western metadata schemas often force Indigenous knowledge into ill-fitting categories, stripping away context and spiritual significance.

To mitigate this, the HDP's `metadata_mapping` module must be utilized not just for schema compliance, but for *ethical contextualization*:

- **Authority to Control (CARE):** Users should utilize HDP's exclusion filters to prevent the ingestion of sensitive subdirectories, respecting the provenance and ownership of the data as defined by the community [73].
- **Responsibility (CARE):** Metadata descriptions generated via the `LLMProcessor` should be prompted to include attribution statements or "CARE Notices" that reflect the community's worldview, rather than relying solely on generic archival descriptions [72, 73].

9.4.3 Operationalizing Ethics in the Pipeline

Ultimately, software cannot automate ethics, but it can provide the mechanisms for ethical decision-making. The HDP's architecture facilitates the decoupling of *preservation* (managed locally via `.hdpc` project states) from *publication* (upload to Zenodo). This aligns with the view that digitization should support *participatory archives*, where communities are active partners in the selection and presentation of their heritage [72]. By allowing users to curate specific batches for publication while retaining others in local-only storage, HDP enables a workflow where Indigenous Data Sovereignty is respected, ensuring that data functions as a resource for collective benefit rather than extraction [73, 74]. By placing these curation tools directly in the hands of communities, the system fosters the technical capacity building required to transform abstract rights into actionable data practices [75].

9.5 Ethical Risks in Digital Dissemination: Trafficking, Sensitivity, and Security

While HDP streamlines the publication process, the uncritical dissemination of high-resolution heritage data introduces significant risks that must be managed through the system's configuration features. The transition from local storage to global platforms transforms heritage assets into accessible digital commodities, necessitating a careful evaluation of the nature and method of data sharing.

9.5.1 Countering the Illicit Trade and Looting

The automation of uploads must not facilitate the illicit antiquities market. Votey [76] demonstrates that digital platforms have become central nodes in the trafficking of cultural goods, where the ease of sharing images and connecting buyers bypasses traditional regulatory checkpoints. Furthermore, Rouhani [77] warns that "open data" is not inherently benign; the publication of precise geospatial coordinates and high-resolution site maps can be utilized to facilitate looting or unauthorized excavations, particularly in conflict zones or politically unstable regions.

To address this, HDP users should utilize the `exclusion_filters` to strip sensitive geolocation metadata from public uploads or withhold high-resolution survey data from the open Zenodo record, retaining them in the local `.hdpc` database for restricted access.

9.5.2 Bioarchaeological Ethics and Contextualization

Specific ethical safeguards are required when processing human remains. Ulguim [78] argues that sharing 3D models of human remains without adequate contextual metadata risks dehumanizing the subject, reducing ancestors to mere “technical showcases” stripped of their osteobiographical narrative. The lack of consent or community consultation in these uploads can constitute an ethical violation. HDP’s metadata enforcement ensures that models are not uploaded as orphan files; the system requires the association of descriptive metadata (such as provenance, age, and ethical statements) before a batch is cleared for publication, preventing the de-contextualization that is prevalent on platforms like Sketchfab [78].

9.5.3 Intellectual Property and Geometric Protection

Finally, the protection of the digital asset itself remains a concern for custodians. Koller [79] highlight that curators are often reluctant to share high-fidelity 3D models due to the risk of intellectual property theft and unauthorized commercial reproduction (e.g., 3D printing of museum artifacts). While HDP currently uploads file-based assets, its modular architecture supports the integration of future components that could implement “remote rendering” or geometric decimation [79]. This capability allows users to share low-resolution proxies for public visualization while securely archiving the high-resolution geometry locally, balancing the mandate for public access with the imperative of data security [77].

10 System Availability and Development Status

The HDP is currently released as open-source software under the GNU General Public License v3.0 (GPLv3) [80]. The source code, binary releases, and technical documentation are available on GitHub³.

10.1 Current Release State

The software described in this manuscript represents the complete architectural design and intended functionality of the HDP system. At the time of writing, the publicly available release (version `v0.1.0-alpha.5`) is in an **Alpha** stage of development. Consequently, readers should be aware that not all features or modules discussed in this paper are fully implemented in the latest public distribution. The current codebase serves primarily as a proof-of-concept for the proposed architecture, with core functionalities operational but advanced features potentially disabled or subject to change.

10.2 Usage and Stability Disclaimer

This software is provided for testing, experimentation, and feedback purposes only. As is standard for alpha-stage research software, there is no guarantee of reliability, correctness, or continuous availability. It is not recommended for deployment in production environments or for use in safety-critical systems without extensive local validation. Furthermore, backward compatibility for project files (`.hdpc`) and configuration schemas is intended, but not guaranteed during this phase, as APIs and data models may evolve significantly between versions. We invite the Digital Humanities community to participate in the testing process and to consult the repository for the most up-to-date implementation roadmap.

11 Conclusion

The preservation of digital cultural heritage demands a shift from ad-hoc, disparate data management practices to standardized, reproducible engineering systems. The HDP represents a significant architectural advancement in this domain, offering a robust solution to the friction between heterogeneous research data

³<https://github.com/Digital-Humanities-Jena/heritage-data-processor>

and rigorous archival standards.

By introducing the persistent `.hdpc` project state, HDP effectively decouples data preparation from immediate upload, allowing for asynchronous curation workflows that were previously difficult to manage with transient scripts. The strict modularity of the Pipeline Component ecosystem addresses the dependency management challenges endemic to complex preservation pipelines, ensuring that processing logic remains portable and reproducible across institutions. Furthermore, the dual-interface design democratizes access to these advanced tools: the Electron-based GUI lowers the technical barrier for users and domain experts, while the comprehensive CLI and REST API provide data engineers with the headless automation capabilities required for institutional-scale ingestion.

11.1 Future Developments

With the architectural foundations of the `hpc-connector` and WebHDP established, future development will broaden its scope to address not only the federation of resources and data lifecycle resilience, but also the integration of active preservation strategies, automated ethical governance protocols, and embedded on-device intelligence.

- **Federated Research Infrastructure:** The convergence of WebHDP and the HPC connector will enable a “Federated Processing” model. Future releases will allow multiple users via the WebHDP interface to submit jobs to a shared, authenticated HPC backend, transitioning beyond the current single-user local client model.
- **Expanded Component Registry:** The Component Registry will be enhanced to support complex, hardware-dependent configurations declared in the `component.yaml`, such as CUDA versions for GPU-accelerated modules.
- **Repository Agnosticism:** While currently optimized for Zenodo, the modular architecture will be abstracted further to support additional emergent repository standards. This ensures HDP serves as a universal bridge for digital heritage preservation, necessitating further evaluations of available repository infrastructures.

11.1.1 State Re-hydration and Large-Collection Resilience

A critical area for optimization addresses the retrieval limitation inherent in the Zenodo REST API, which caps record retrieval at 10,000 items. While the HDP currently mitigates this by treating the local `.hdpc` database as the source of truth, the loss of this local file poses a significant risk for large-scale collections, effectively compromising synchronization integrity.

To resolve this, future iterations will implement a **State Re-hydration Utility** designed for recovering metadata related to the processed records. Distinct from the standard REST API, this module will leverage the **OAI-PMH** (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) interface [81]. By utilizing OAI-PMH’s flow control and resumption tokens, the utility will be capable of iteratively harvesting metadata for collections of arbitrary size to reconstruct the local `zenodo_records` table. This ensures that the local project state can always be fully reconstituted from the remote archive, guaranteeing system resilience and data continuity regardless of local storage failures.

11.1.2 Active Preservation and Default Format Normalization

Addressing the distinction between *bit-level preservation* (ensured by Zenodo) and *functional preservation*, future iterations of the HDP will introduce an integrated **Active Preservation Layer**. While the repository guarantees that the stored bitstream remains unchanged, it does not guard against the functional obsolescence of proprietary file formats.

To mitigate this, the pipeline will implement **Automated Format Normalization** as a default, “opt-out”

behavior during the ingestion phase. Upon detecting proprietary or risk-prone formats (e.g., camera-specific RAW files, proprietary 3D binaries, or closed document formats), the system will automatically generate a normalized, open-standard derivative (e.g., uncompressed TIFF, PDF/A, or ASCII-based OBJ) to serve as the long-term archival copy. By ensuring that every deposited record contains at least one representation in a documented, non-proprietary standard, the HDP effectively shifts the preservation strategy from passive storage to active risk management, ensuring the data remains interpretable by future scholarship independent of specific software vendors.

11.1.3 Automated Sensitivity Detection and Ethical Guardrails

Another key area for future development is the integration of an “Automated Sensitivity Detection” middleware within the HDP pipeline. While the current architecture streamlines ingestion, it relies on the user’s manual discretion to identify sensitive materials. To better align with the CARE Principles [73], future iterations will implement algorithmic safeguards designed to flag potential ethical risks prior to repository upload.

Geospatial Redaction and “Red Lists” To mitigate the risks of looting and site exploitation facilitated by open data, the detector will analyze file metadata (EXIF/XMP) for high-precision geolocation coordinates. By cross-referencing these coordinates against defined *risk zones* (such as areas of active conflict or known looting hotspots) [76, 77], the system will automatically prompt the user to redact spatial data or restrict the record’s access level. This functionality aims to prevent the misuse of heritage data while maintaining the scholarly value of the non-spatial dataset [77].

Bioarchaeological and Sacred Content Flagging Building on the challenges of digital bioarchaeology, the system will employ metadata keyword scanning and potentially computer vision heuristics to identify human remains or sacred objects. Upon detection, the pipeline will halt the batch processing for those specific records, requiring the operator to explicitly confirm the presence of ethical contextualization, such as osteobiographies or consent statements [78]. This human-in-the-loop (HITL) friction is intentional, designed to prevent the inadvertent “datafication” of ancestors or sensitive indigenous knowledge [72].

Integration with Local Contexts Finally, the HDP will move toward direct integration with the *Local Contexts* Hub API. This will allow users to apply Traditional Knowledge (TK) and Biocultural (BC) Labels directly within the `metadata_mapping` wizard. By embedding these persistent digital identifiers into the `.hdpc` database, the system ensures that Indigenous authority and governance protocols travel with the data, regardless of the repository environment [73, 74]. By embedding these ethical and technical standards directly into the processing architecture, HDP ensures that the future of digital heritage is not only persistent but also culturally responsive and technically reproducible.

11.1.4 Embedded Intelligence via Small Language Models

To enhance the system’s cognitive capabilities without compromising the *local-first* privacy architecture or requiring high-end workstation hardware, future releases will integrate optimized Small Language Models (SLMs) directly into the client application. Specifically, the system will leverage high-efficiency models such as *Qwen3-4B-Instruct-2507* [82] to provide real-time, on-device intelligence.

This embedded module will be utilized for granular tasks including metadata mapping suggestions, semantic validation of descriptive fields, and contextual UI hinting. Recognizing the variability in user hardware environments, this feature is designed with a strict “opt-in” performance toggle; users can enable the module for advanced assistance during complex curation tasks or disable it entirely to prioritize system responsiveness on lower-specification machines.

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